

THE MUTUAL EFFECTS OF SHEAR AND TRANSVERSE DAMAGE IN POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The understanding of matrix failure is of paramount importance, due to its complexity and effect on the structural behavior of the laminate. While transverse and shear damage are often treated independently, the associated cracks are similar in appearance and effect. Matrix damage is often quantified by its crack density. However, damage also can be presented as a state variable. The definition of damage state variables and their evolution laws are the foundation of continuum damage mechanics approaches, yet the available experimental data for shear damage evolution is limited. This paper focused on the shear modulus reduction due to transverse cracks and the evolution of transverse and shear damage variables. A modified Iosipescu coupon was designed to study the evolution of shear and transverse damage including their mutual interaction [1]. The layup and coupon geometry were selected in a way that controlled the severity of the damage and allowed the measurement of shear and transverse stiffness degradation experimentally. The proposed method has advantages of easy specimen fabrication and uses a standard test fixture.

2 Material degradation models

The classical approach toward material degradation modeling in fiber reinforced composite materials is describing material stiffness as a function of crack density. There are different analytical, semi-analytical and numerical models which focus on these solutions. Among the analytical models the Hashin model [2,3] and the shear lag theory by Tan et al. [4,5] were selected for this study.

Hashin [2,3] analyzed the stiffness reduction of cracked cross ply laminates by a variational method on the basis of the principle of minimum complementary energy. Axial stiffness reductions

were in good agreement with experimental data but shear modulus reduction was not evaluated.

Tan et al. [4,5] proposed an analytical solution based on a shear lag theory for progressive matrix cracking in a composite laminate. The closed form solutions were obtained for laminate stiffnesses and Poisson's ratio as function of crack density. This analysis only required basic mechanical and thermal properties obtained from uniaxial ply testing. The model was compared with experimental data. However the comparison was done only for the axial stiffness and Poisson's ratio.

Another approach describes damage as a macroscopic state variable and defines material degradation in the framework of continuum damage mechanics [6]. In fiber reinforced composites, matrix damage can be described as cracks either parallel or perpendicular to the fiber direction. A damage tensor D (of rank two or four) can be used to represent damage with principal directions aligned with the material directions.

Ladeveze and La Dantec [7, 8], were among the first to apply a damage mechanics model to composite laminates. In this model, damage mechanics was used to describe the matrix microcracking and fiber/matrix debonding. Ladeveze used different damage variables in shear and the transverse direction. Engblom et al. [9,10] suggested using the same damage variable in all directions. They used the Hashin criterion and assumed a linear relation between shear and transverse damage variables.

Barbero and Lonetti [11], Barbero and Vivo [12], and Barbero et al. [13] proposed a damage model based on a second order damage tensor. A new expression for a damage surface was proposed, which reduced to the expression of the Tsai-Wu failure criterion in stress space. It was assumed that the lamina material directions coincide with the principal damage directions for a lamina as:

$$D_{ij} = d_i \delta_{ij} ; \text{no sum on } i, i, j = 1..3 \quad (1)$$

Therefore, the second order damage tensor can be characterized as a diagonal matrix, where d_i are the eigenvalues of the damage tensor, which represent the damage ratio along principal directions. In this model there was no independent damage variable in the shear direction. Using the constitutive equation in the damaged configuration the shear damage variable was defined as:

$$(1 - d_6) = (1 - d_1)(1 - d_2) \quad (2)$$

The damage models above [11-13] defined a shear damage variable as a linear function of a transverse damage variable.

Thakkar and Pandey [14] proposed a model based on the Hashin failure criterion. This model assumed a plane stress state and damage was assumed to develop separately in the two axes. As with the other models reviewed here, they assumed a linear relation between the shear and transverse damage variables.

Nuimer et al. [5] adopted the shear lag theory solution to find effective in-plane compliance relations of a matrix cracked lamina. They defined D_2 and D_6 as internal state variables representing the lamina damage state directly.

The experimental study of the coupon under transverse load shows after a certain number of cracks, the cracks cannot be formed anymore. Applying more loads after this point may induce another type of damage like delamination, debonding between coupon and end tabs or cracks in the supporting plies. The maximum number of possible transverse cracks in the 90° plies of the laminate is known as the saturation crack density.

Highsmith et al. [15] showed experimentally the saturation transverse crack density for E-glass/epoxy composite laminates depends on the lay-up pattern. Later, Altus et al [16], Ji et al. [17], Schoeppner et al. [18] and Dharani et al. [19] did a comprehensive study on the transverse crack saturation in composite laminate with 90° plies. They found the transverse stress in the 90° plies decreases as the number of cracks increases. The reduction of the transverse stress around the damaged region continues until the transverse stress in the 90° plies actually becomes compressive. However, tensile stress at the supporting layers, near the transverse crack tips,

creates high stress singularity regions which can induce delamination over the interface of the 90° plies and supporting layers.

3 Experimental Work

One reason little data exists comparing the interaction of transverse and shear damage, is the difficulty of inducing axial and shear stress in the same test coupon. Not only must the coupon withstand axial and shear stress, the damage density must also be controlled. The Iosipescu and torsion coupons can induce transverse and shear damage. They have the capability of applying transverse or axial loads and introducing a predetermined crack density. The Iosipescu coupon was considered in this work.

3.1 Coupon Design

The coupon was designed to accommodate both axial and shear loading with controlled crack densities. A modified Iosipescu coupon with a $[0_1/90_7]_S$ layup was used. The characteristic V notches of the Iosipescu coupon were replaced with two slots machined on both sides of the coupon. The notch height was selected to remove only the 90° plies as shown in figure 1. The slotted region formed the coupon gage section where the desired crack density was introduced and was shown to have uniform shear stress when loaded in the Iosipescu test fixture [1]. Under axial tension, transverse damage in the 90° plies occurred at a lower strain than damage in the 0° plies.

Test coupons were fabricated from S-glass/epoxy prepreg using hand lay-up and an autoclave cure. Following the cure of the glass plates, e-glass/epoxy cloth prepreg was applied to the ends of the specimen to provide a compliant load path from the specimen to the grip.

In this experiment, a modified Iosipescu shear fixture was used, where the lower grip was free to slide in axial direction. This modification decreased the axial load and possible bending over the gage area compared to fixed lower grip design. Figure 2 shows the modified Iosipescu test fixture and the free sliding grip.

3.2 Material degradation tests

The displacement and strain of the slotted coupon were measured using digital image correlation (DIC). DIC is a noncontact optical method using images of the test surfaces taken at different load and displacement configurations. In this work images were recorded from two cameras providing a three dimensional description of deformation.

Because of the slotted coupon's increased length, bending effects, while loaded in shear, were a concern. To study the effect of bending on the strain field the axial and shear strain were compared along the line O-O' in figure 3.

Figure 4 shows that the ratio of axial strain to the shear strain is small (less than 3%), leaving the gage section under nearly pure shear loading. The natural distribution of bending strain and the extension of the supporting layer beyond the slots resulted in a low bending strain over the gage section.

The slotted coupons were first subjected to an axial load to introduce transverse damage in the 90° plies. The numbers of cracks were counted using the DIC spatial strain field and the load-displacement curve in situ. The load was stopped when the required number of cracks was achieved. Figure 5 shows the axial shear strain field of the coupons after 1, 3 and 5 cracks which clearly show the crack density.

Figure 6 shows the load-displacement curve for a coupon loaded to 6 cracks. The applied load had a similar decrease after each crack (190 N). The numbers of cracks was checked using a dye penetrant, which agreed with the in situ measures. To measure the transverse stiffness reduction from the transverse cracks, the axial test was repeated. The second axial test was done with a maximum load of 40% UTS to measure the elastic axial stiffness without inducing further damage.

After the axial test, shear was applied using the modified Iosipescu fixture with a cross head speed of 0.5 mm/min. The displacement and strain of the coupons with pre-existing transverse damage were recorded using DIC and averaged over the gage section. The linear part of the shear stress-strain curve was used to determine shear modulus.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Material degradation analysis

Material softening or damage was observed in the axial tests of the slotted coupons as shown in figure

7. The loading curves nearly coincided while the slope of the reloading curves was proportional to the transverse crack density. The stress-strain curves showed approximately the same stress reduction after each crack; showing that all cracks were of similar size. The damage was primarily in the form of transverse cracks in the 90° plies. The slope of the reloading curve was used to obtain the axial laminate stiffness reduction.

Figure 8 compares the experimental axial stiffness reduction with shear lag theory [4,5] and the Hashin model [2], where E_{x0} is the initial axial stiffness of the intact laminate. The agreement is generally favorable, particularly at the higher crack densities. The prediction of the shear lag and Hashin model for axial stiffness reduction is exactly the same even though they use different methods for the simulation of the material stiffness degradation.

Figure 9 compares the experimental shear modulus reduction with shear lag theory and Hashin's model. The comparison shows that these analytical models overestimate the shear modulus reduction, particularly at higher crack densities. Interestingly, both analytical models tend to agree at all crack densities. The difference between the models and experiment suggest that a shear mechanism has not been properly described.

One possible reason for the difference between the predicted and experimental shear modulus reduction is friction between the crack faces. Frictional forces between crack faces transmit shear and would tend to increase the shear modulus, particularly in the presence of axial compression. The transverse stiffness is not sensitive to friction along the crack faces, which explains agreement in that direction.

4.2 Damage evolution

To study material degradation in the framework of continuum damage mechanics, the damage variables and evolution models should be defined.

Two methods were used to describe damage. In the first method damage was defined for the whole laminate including the 90° plies and supporting layers. In this case the laminate was defined as a continuum body for which damage should be defined. In this approach, damage represents the laminate stiffness reduction.

Figure 10 compares the experimental values of d_2^L and d_6^L where damage caused less softening in shear

than in the transverse direction. The general proportionality between d_2^t and d_6^t expressed by all the models for damage less than 0.5 was not observed experimentally.

In the second method, damage was defined only for the 90° plies by assuming there was no damage in supporting layers. Here damage represents stiffness reduction in the damaged 90° plies not the whole laminate. To calculate damage, the following procedure was applied for every test case. Damage from the axial load in the 90° plies, E_2 , was inferred from changes in E_x using lamination theory and assuming no damage in the 0° plies. The shear modulus was found from the Iosipescu shear tests in the same way as the transverse damage, then the damage variables were calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} d_2 &= 1 - \frac{E_2}{E_2^0} \\ d_6 &= 1 - \frac{G_{12}}{G_{12}^0} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where d_2 was the damage ratio in the transverse direction and d_6 was the damage ratio in the shear direction, E_2^0 and G_{12}^0 were the undamaged transverse and shear moduli. Table 1 shows the damage variables for each crack density.

Figure 11 compares the experimental values of d_2 and d_6 where less softening was again observed in shear than in the transverse direction. The analytical models are less similar to the linear models than was observed for laminate damage in figure 10. While the analytical models agree better with experiment than the linear models, both types of models do not fully described the lower shear softening observed experimentally.

A regression analysis showed that shear and transverse damage were related by

$$(1 - d_6) = (1 - d_2)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (4)$$

Equation 4 is included in figure 11 for comparison.

4.3 Upper limit for damage variables

Damage variables theoretically can be increased to 1. In terms of material properties, this means the residual stiffness goes to zero. Considering the study of the transverse crack saturation, there is a maximum value (upper band) for the transverse

damage variable which is called d_{2u} . Increasing the load beyond where d_{2u} occurs changes the damage mechanism for damage. In a continuum damage model the simulation of transverse damage evolution should take d_{2u} into account.

In this work the compressive stress criterion was used to find the transverse crack saturation. To find the stress components in the 90° plies, a finite element model was used. Three dimensional finite element models of the slotted coupons were created (ABAQUS, version #6.11). A symmetry plane was defined along length of the coupon so that half of the coupon was modeled. A 20 node iso-parametric brick element was used for the whole model except the notch area around the slot region where quadratic tetrahedron elements were used.

Using the finite element model, the longitudinal normal stress distribution at the laminate mid-plane along the line C-C' is plotted as shown in figures 12 and 13. In figure 13 the stress is normalized by its far field value for different crack densities. The plot shows the axial stress is tensile at the midplane for the crack densities less than 2.4 cracks/cm while it is compressive for the crack densities greater than 2.4 cracks/cm, implying a saturation crack density of approximately 2.4 cracks/cm. Also the stress distribution is almost the same for cracks density up to 1.2 cracks/cm. The maximum longitudinal stress starts to decrease for crack densities higher than 1.2 cracks/cm. To more accurately find the saturation crack density the normalized longitudinal normal stress at point C' between two cracks was plotted versus crack density was plotted in Figure 14. The results show that 2.35 cracks/cm can be defined as the transverse crack density saturation for this lay-up. The experimental investigation also confirmed that after 2.4 cracks/cm the laminate reaches a saturation state. Increasing the load after 2.4 cracks/cm resulted in other types of damage without additional transverse cracks. Using figure 8 the value of E_2 was determined for the saturation crack density of 2.35 cracks/cm and then the value of d_{2u} for this lay-up was calculated by equation (3). Considering the value of d_{2u} for $[0/90_7]_s$ lay-up and using equation (11) the transverse and shear damage relationship can be modified as

$$(1 - d_6) = (1 - d_2)^{0.25} \quad \text{if } d_2 \leq 0.65 \quad (5)$$

5 Conclusions

The lack of experimental data for shear damage evolution has hindered our understanding of mutual effects between matrix damage variables. This study investigated the relationship of transverse and shear damage experimentally. A modified Iosipescu coupon was designed. Transverse damage was introduced to the specimens after which they were loaded using a modified Iosipescu shear test. The experimental results showed the common assumption of a linear relation between matrix damage variables is not correct. Shear damage was found as the fourth root of transverse damage. An upper limit for damage was determined experimentally and verified numerically.

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Crack density (cracks/cm)	Damage variables	
	d ₂	d ₆
0.4	0.23	0.051
0.8	0.37	0.099
1.2	0.47	0.157
1.6	0.53	0.205
2.0	0.59	0.220
2.4	0.65	0.241

Table 1. Damage variables for every test case

Fig.1. Slotted shear/tension coupon

Fig 4. The ratio of axial strain due to bending over the shear strain across the O-O' section

Fig 2. The modified Iosipescu test fixture and the free sliding direction

Fig 3. Slotted coupon used to study bending while loaded in shear.

Fig 5. Strain distribution for different cracks densities under axial loading

Fig 6. The load-displacement curve for a coupon with six cracks

Fig. 7. The axial stress- strain curve of a 2.4 cracks/cm coupon and reloading curves for all test cases

Fig 8. Cracked laminate axial stiffness reduction

Fig 9. Cracked laminate shear modulus reduction

Fig 10. Shear damage vs transverse damage for the whole laminate

Fig 11. Shear damage vs transverse damage for 90° plies

Fig 12. Laminate containing cracked plies

Fig 13. Normalized longitudinal normal stress along the longitudinal direction C-C'' (figure 12) for various transverse crack densities.

Fig 14. The variation of the normalized longitudinal normal stress verses crack density at point C' (figure 12).